

SHINOSIY'S LIFE AND ACTIVITIES

Toshpulatova Mohinur Tolib qizi

ToshDO'TAU O'zbek filologiyasi fakulteti 4-kurs

mohinurtoshpulatova@gmail.com

+998940505202

Abstract Shinosiy lived and worked during the reign of Feruz II and was a talented poet and musician. Information about his life and work is based on the notes in Hasanmurod Laffasiy's "Tazkirai shuaro," Bobojon Tarroh Xodim's "Xorazm shoirlari va navozandalari," Bayoniy's "Shajarayi Xorazmshohiy," and Ahmad Tabibiy's "Majmuat ush-shuaroiy payravi Feruzshohiy."

The article talks about Shinosiy's life path, leadership activity, his written memoirs and poems, and sources cited in the publication. Shinosiy's life and literary heritage were studied in terms of literary criticism and textual analysis.

Key words: Shinosiy, leadership, memoirist, poet, memoir, ghazal, bayat, Jomiytimsol, Muhammadmurod Devonbegi.

The end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century is a special era in the cultural and literary life of the Khiva Khanate. During this period, science, literature, arts, and translation flourished. Skilled poets were especially invited to the palace of Muhammad Rahim Khan II, the ruler, which created a broad opportunity for the development of music and literature. The palace poets played a significant role in the advancement of music and literature in Khiva Khanate. During this period, accomplished musicians, as well as the poet Shinosiy, the son of Shayxnazar Muhammadmurod Devanbegi, who is known for his poem "G'azal ichra Jomiytimsol," lived and worked in the palace.

Shinosiy was born in Khiva. The year of his birth is not precisely mentioned in Hasanmurod Laffasiy's "Tazkirayi shuaro." However, his death is recorded as 1918 (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 53). In Bobojon Tarroh-Xodim's "Xorazm shoir va

navozandalari" tazkira, it is mentioned that the poet died at the age of 40 (Xodim, 2011, p.79). According to the information provided by Hasanmurod Laffasiy and Bobojon Tarroh-Xodim, it is known that Shinosiy was born between 1877-1878.

Xodim stated the following regarding Shinosiy's emergence: "... Said Muhammadhon, Muhammad Rahim's second son, purchased Muhammadmurod Devanbegi and raised him as his servant. At that time, Muhammad Rahim II was eighteen years old.

After several years, following the death of Said Muhammadhon, and with Muhammad Rahim II assuming the throne after his father, he conferred upon Muhammadmurod the title of "Devonbegi" and named him after his father as Shayxnazar. Henceforth, he was known by this name. According to Xodim, it is possible to assume that Shayxnazar was released from the servitude of Muhammad Rahim II and his family when he became an established poet in society. (Xodim, 2011, pp. 75-76).

In the Bayoniy's "Shajarayi Xorazmshohiy," Shinosiy is mentioned as the third son of Muhammadmurod Devanbegi. His eldest son was Husayn Muhammadboy (who was appointed as a devonbegi after his father's death) wrote gazals with the pen name Noziriy. The second son was Omomkeldiboy. Bayoniy also recorded Shinosiy's paternal uncles, including Qutlug' Qadam, Qutlimurodboy, and Khudoyberganboy (Bayoniy, Inv. 9596). Bayoniy also provided information regarding Shinosiy's grandfather, stating "Shayxnazar's maternal grandfather was the lord of Islomkhoja, and his grandmother was Saodatjonbeka" (Xodim, 2011, p.77).

In Salomat Matkarimova's dissertation "Tabibiy - tazkiranavis," she mentioned that Shinosiy was Bayoniy's nephew. However, she did not provide a citation for the source of this information (Matkarimova, 2007, p.34).

According to Laffasiy's tazkira, Shinosiy studied at the same school with his brother (Husayn Muhammadboy Nozir) in Khiva under the guidance of Inoyatulla

Okhund, a renowned Khorezm scholar (Laffasiy, 1992, p.52). Xodim's tazkira, on the other hand, stated that Shinosiy attended a primary school but did not receive a religious education, yet he remained a faithful Muslim (Xodim, 2011, p.76).

Laffasiy noted that Shinosiy's father, Muhammadmurod Devanbegi, had been the governor of Kokand. "... He used to admonish and punish ignorant people, and occupied himself with agriculture, giving peace and safety to the Uzbek population in the Khorezm region. The group of rebels, under Shayxnazar's political agenda, intimidated the people, but under his father's governance, they were peacefully engaged in agriculture" (Laffasiy, 1992, p.52).

According to Xodim, during the reign of Feruz Khan, Shinosiy was also given the titles of yasavulboshi and askarboshi, and he was noted to be a brave and courageous warrior, known for his exploits in battle. Xodim described him as "a deceased hero who pierced the eye of the hawk with an arrow" (Xodim, 2011, p.77).

After Feruz Khan's death, Shinosiy served as yasavulboshi during the reign of Isfandiyor Khan (1910-1918). He was naturally a brave and just person, and even if he knew the wrath of the khan, he did not act against his conscience. Isfandiyor Khan ordered Shinosiy to execute the scholar and statesman of his time, Islomkhodja (1872-1913). Shinosiy replied: "Your Majesty, you are the sovereign of Khorezm. If you call for Islomkhodja, call for me too. I will kneel and bow my head before you," (Xodim, 2011, p.77) giving an uncompromising response. This incident may have been one of the reasons for Shinosiy's later tragic death.

It is possible that one of the reasons why Shinosiy refused to follow the khan's order was due to his friendship with Islomkhodja, who was the husband of Shinosiy's maternal aunt, Saodatjonbek. However, looking at history, we can also see that Islomkhodja was an active participant in establishing various institutions in Khorezm and other cities, such as post and telegraph offices, hospitals, madrasas, and modern schools, including Russian schools. He also established relationships with foreign countries. For his services in organizing the government, he was

awarded the title of "Vaziri Akbar." Therefore, intentionally killing such a person would have been unjustified.

After the death of Islomkhodja, Ashur Mahram is appointed in his place. Due to certain reasons, the relationships between Ashur Mahram and one of the Turkmen officials, "Durdi Vakil", deteriorate. After that, the Turkmen tribe led by Junaid Khan begins to march towards Khiva. Isfandiyor Khan sends reinforcements against the Turkmen bandits under the command of Shinosiy.

Shinosiy led an extensive battle against a gang of bandits, according to Isfandiyor's command. According to the hagiographical memoirs of Laffasiy, he defeated the violent brigands led by Shommikal (1331 AH/1913) from among the ignorant riff-raff, Shomurod Bakhshi, and Qurban Muhammad Sardor (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 53).

In the beginning of June 1915, under Nikolai II's orders, General Fyodor Martson (1914-1916) arrived in Khiva from Tashkent. Later, Isfandiyor punished Shinosiy by sending him to Olmota pass for eighteen months, which was also carried out in 1911 with all of his brothers, by appointing him to "Visilka". (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 53).

In fact, in 1911, Isfandiyor had imprisoned Shinosiy along with all of his brothers for eighteen months. Despite these events, Isfandiyor Khan carried out his orders justly and "in 1918, Isfandiyor Khan ordered Shinosiy to be killed." (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 53). According to the information, his elder brother Noziriy was also killed in that year (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 50). According to Bobojon Tarrokh's information, he was buried in Chodir Eshon's tomb (Khodim, 2011, p. 79).

Shinosiy was a powerful leader of his time and was also known to be a talented poet who managed to compile poetry books. According to Laffasiy's memoirs, "Shayxnazar served as governor in Khorezm for many years. After the death of his father, Muhammadmurod devonbegi, he resigned from his post and came to Khiva. In the service of Feruz Muhammad Rahim Khan, he devoted his service and assumed

the moniker Shinosiy. He wrote ghazals and various types of poetry for Feruz. But the beauty and the meaning of Shinosiy's poetry is like a pearl in relation to its content, and they were able to produce unique gems of knowledge from it." (Laffasiy, 1992, p. 52). Bobojon Tarrokh's memoirs also state that Shinosiy was engaged in poetry at the age of thirty. (Khodim, 2011, p. 79).

Shayxnazar wrote poems under the pseudonym of Shinosiy. The pseudonym 'Shinosiy' is derived from the verb 'shinoxtan' which means to know or recognize, and the noun 'bilimdon' which means knowledgeable (فرهنگ تفسیری زبان تاجیکی) (Forscha-tojikcha lug'at, 2008, p. 643).

According to Ahmad Tabibiy's "Majmuat ush-shuaroyi payravi Feruzshohiy" (Tabibiy, inv.1152) memoir, among the thirty-three poets, Shinosiy is also mentioned as being one of the poets who contributed to the ghazals of Feruz. In this collection, Shinosiy's poems were listed in the tenth position and repeated in that order. Gulsara Ismoilova notes the uniqueness of Tabibiy's work, stating, "In Tabibiy's masnavi, he gives importance to the literary position and poetic value of each poet, regardless of whether they were affiliated with a certain class or were considered to be ordinary citizens." (Ismoilova, 1995, pp. 32-33).

Hasanmurod Laffasiy's "Tazkirayi shuaro" features a couplets with the opening verse "Zihi sun'ing qilib bu gumbazu davvorni barpo" and two ghazals with the refrain "Bois". In addition, Laffasiy composed an eight-line masnavi about Shinosiy. In his masnavis, Laffasiy expresses praise for Shinosiy.

“Shinosiyki bor fazli haqshunos,

Onga fahmi donish erur beqiyos.

Tatabbu’ tarikin qilib ixtiyor,

Bu nazm ichra ko‘rguzgusi iqtidor”.

Shinosiy organized a collection of poems. In 1907-1908, the poet and calligrapher Bobojon Tarroh and the calligrapher Mullah Boltaniyoz Xattot Nadim copied the collection. A manuscript of Shinosiy's collection is preserved at the East

Literature Institute of Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences under the numbers 911 and 951. Shinosiy's collection was also published in the Xiva stone library (Khidoyatov, 2011, p.76).

There have not been any specific studies on Shinosiy's activity. However, research on the literary environment of Khorezm provides little information about him. For instance, in her dissertation "The Literary Environment of Feruz's Era in Khorezm," Gulnara Ismoilova states the following information about Shinosiy's collection: "In order to explore the life and creativity of this prolific poet, we searched through the Abu Rayhan Beruni Oriental Studies Institute and the manuscripts collection of the Institute of Manuscripts named after Hamid Sulaymonov to determine whether or not he had organized poetic collections. As a result of our search, we discovered that two collections of his poems, one consisting of small size ghazals named Abu Raykhan Beruni (951, 911-II) and the other consisting of 2679 poems, are preserved in the Institute of Manuscripts named after Hamid Sulaymonov" (Ismoilova, 1995, pp.35-36).

In her dissertation "Mutrib Khanakharov and His Literary Heritage," Sohiba Madirimova notes that a collection of poems titled "Devoni Mutrib Khanakharov," which is preserved in the Hamid Sulaymon manuscript collection of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, contains two parts. In the first part, there are poems by Shinosiy, and in the second part, there are poems by Mutrib Khanakharov. According to Madirimova, "The dimensions of the collection are 27.5x17.5 cm, and it consists of 508 pages. Shinosiy's poems are presented from page 1^b to page 81^a..." [Madirimova, 2021, p. 22].

Many of Shinosiy's ghazals are preserved in the manuscript collections of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences under the numbers 1152, 1172, 1175, 1176, 1182, 1184, 1190, 1191, 1192, 1196, 2036, 1275, 1129, 6927, 6930, 6932, 6969, 6971, 6990, 7032, and 2024. They are also preserved in the State Literature Museum

named after Alisher Navoi under the number 582 and in the Ichon-Qala Museum in Khiva under the numbers 5894/II, 5894/III, 5894/IV, 5894/V, and 5884/V.

In addition to ghazals, his poems in the Muxamma genre are also preserved in the manuscript collections of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences under the numbers 1130, 1127, 1131, 1133, 1134, and 1157. These collections of Muxammas poems are also preserved in the manuscript collections of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences.

The study of Shinosiy's literary heritage, analyzing the sources of his collections, and applying text and manuscript analysis approaches are among the relevant issues in modern studies.

References:

1. Лаффасий, Ҳасанмурод. (1992) Тазкираи шуаро (Нашрга тайёрловчи: Бобожонов П.). – Урганч: Хоразм. –Б. 50-55.
2. Бобожон Тарроҳ-Ходим. (2011) Хоразм шоир ва навозандалари. –Тошкент, Тафаккур қаноти. –Б. 74-79;
3. Баёний, Муҳаммад Юсуф. Шажараи хоразмшоҳий. ЎзР ФА ШИ қўлёзмалар фонди, инв. № 9596.
4. Маткаримова, С. (2007). Табибий – тазкиранавис. (136). Филол. фан. номз. дисс. Тошкент.
5. Madirimova, S. (2019). Mutrib Xonaxarob asarlari qo 'lyozmalarining ilmiy tavsifi. *Oltin bitiglar–Golden Scripts*, 3(3).
6. Мадиримова, С. М. (2018). О СЮЖЕТЕ ПОЭМЫ «АШИК ГАРИБ И ШАХСАНАМ». *Редакционная коллегия*, 109.
7. Jabbarov, N. (2010). What is education. *Tashkent. Ma'naviyat*.
8. Mirzakarimovna, R. D. (2022). Literary-aesthetic thinking-a factor of renewal of poetic image in tavallo's work. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(5), 195-199.